

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D2.2

Citizen Science Hubs Governance Framework and Operating Models

Citizen Science Center Zurich

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D2.2: Citizen Science Hubs Governance Framework & Operating Models

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MAIN AUTHORS

Name	Organisation
Rosy Mondardini, Ursina Roffler	CC-CS
Monika Mačiulienė, Aelita Skaržauskienė	VG TU
Estratios Stylianidis	AUTH
Xavier Arino Vila, Begoña Miñarro Vivas, Sofia Mojica Baquero	UAB
Maya van den Berg	UT
Christos Politis	Q-Plan

QUALITY REVIEWERS

Name	Organisation
Sabine Wildevuur	UT
Greta Nasi	SDA Bocconi

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Executive Summary

INCENTIVE's aim is to empower European Research Performing and Funding Organizations (RPFOS) to establish sustainable transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent Citizen Science (CS). These "Citizen Science Hubs" (CSHs) will provide appropriate channels and means to initiate, design and conduct CS projects. By engaging and responding to needs for expertise and knowledge of all stakeholders of the RPFOS, the hubs will allow active and responsible participation in science, unleashing the untapped potential of CS for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).

Such CSHs need to be fully integrated in their founding institutions and adopt the strategic outlooks necessary to sustainably embody them with the overall institutional operations (facilities, organisational structure, processes, standards, regulations, resources, etc.). To this goal, four RPFOS of the INCENTIVE consortium - namely Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Autonomous University of Barcelona, University of Twente, and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University - have taken up the challenge to design the implementation of their own institutional hub, addressing conceptual and operational parts, as well as the RRI-related aspects. Via a series of multi-stakeholder interactions, including co-creation workshops (Task 2.1), surveys, group discussions, and individual conversations, and in a spirit of constant exchanges and mutual learning, governance frameworks and operating models were drafted for and by each of the INCENTIVE's RPFOS.

While the RPFOS are ultimately responsible for designing, setting up, and operating their CSHs, the consortium's partners provided inspiration with a set of baseline elements for the governance, operating, and monitoring model of the hubs, and guidance with the core principle of RRI. This report 'Citizen Science Hubs Governance Frameworks and Operating Models' is outlining the methodology and the findings of Task 2.2 that aims to design the governance structure and operating model of the CSHs for each partner RPFOS, including the procedures required to sustainably embody the CSH with the overall operation of the RPFOS (facilities, organizational structure, processes, standards, regulations, resources, etc.). Also, this task build on the work of other Work Packages, namely WP2 Task 2.1 "Co-creating the Citizen Science Hubs with key stakeholders" and WP4 Task 4.1 "Designing the INCENTIVE monitoring, evaluation and assessment framework".

1. Introduction

1.1 About INCENTIVE and the Citizen Science Hubs

INCENTIVE is set on empowering European Research Performing and Funding Organizations (RPFOS) to establish sustainable transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent Citizen Science (CS). These hubs, named here “Citizen Science Hubs” (CSHs), use CS as a way of: Improving the quality, depth, and impact of research; interacting with society in meaningful and deeply transformative ways, and transforming the outcomes of CS projects into follow-up projects and policy recommendations.

In INCENTIVE, CSHs are defined as follows: *“A scientific organisation (or part of a scientific organisation) with the purpose to initiate, execute, promote and coordinate participatory Research and Innovation (R&I) with and for citizens. As such, CSHs based in Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) are tasked to empower their internal and external stakeholders to co-create new knowledge in a transdisciplinary way, forging new stakeholder interactions and grounding Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in society.”*

A key element distinguishing CSHs from other knowledge transfer mechanisms (technology transfer offices, SciShops, etc.) is that these hubs engage and respond to needs for expertise and knowledge of *all* stakeholders of RPFOS – namely researchers, citizens and civil society organisations, industry, and government – via cooperative, active and responsible participation in science. Thereby, the CSHs promote:

- Participation in projects established by scientists (citizens contribute data, observations, etc.);
- Participation in governing, financing or setting the agenda of projects established by scientists;
- Stakeholders taking the lead in initiating, co-designing, and conducting projects (e.g., setting new research questions or business problems, asking for peer reviews and seeking to evaluate public policies).

These extended forms of R&I, with stakeholders participating in science, hold promising and untapped potential of CS for RRI.

Through INCENTIVE, CSHs will be established in four RPFOS, namely four EU Universities:

- University of Twente (the Netherlands);
- Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain);
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece);
- Vilnius Tech University (Lithuania).

The CSHs will be fully integrated in the R&I governance and operation system of their founding institutions and adopt strategic outlooks that support their sustainable and adaptive operation beyond the lifespan of elected administrations and finite funding schemes, profoundly contributing to the opening of science to their social, economic, environmental, and cultural realm.

Objective 2 of INCENTIVE – of which Task 2.2 is part – foresees the development of tailored governance and operating models for the CSH of each RPFOS with engaged roles, incentives and activities for all R&I stakeholders. The stakeholders’ societal needs, values and requirements drive the co-creation of the

framework for the establishment of CSHs. To this end, the four RPFOs co-created their own tailored CSH governance and operating models, addressing the vision, resources, organisational structure, as well as the RRI-related aspects of those hubs' operation.

1.2 About this deliverable

The aim of this Task (T2.2) was to design the Governance Frameworks and Operating Models for each CSH, in collaboration with the respective RPFO. This included the procedures required to sustainably embody the CSH with the overall institutional operations (facilities, organisational structure, processes, standards, regulations, resources, etc.). To this end, based on the knowledge gathered from WP 1 and the baseline governance and operating models co-created in T2.1, this task focused on developing the four CSH governance frameworks and operating models. In particular, the following aspects were defined:

1. The **vision and objectives** of the CSHs;
2. The **facilities** that will be used as single points of contact for R&I co-creation (be they physical – within or near the University – and/or virtual) along with their standards;
3. The **organizational structure, roles and responsibilities** of the implementation team dedicated to the CSHs (i.e., Secretariat, Facilitator, Community Manager, Trainers) as well as the Board of Directors and the Stakeholder Board;
4. The **procedures for the use of the CSH** by the professional researchers of the RPFO as well as by the key stakeholders;
5. The **code of conduct** defining the rights and obligations of all parties involved, addressing ethical and legal considerations (e.g., informed consent procedures, guidelines for the ownership of data, appropriate processes to handle disputes, etc.);
6. The **RRI-related principles** pertaining to all the activities of the CSH, including gender equality provisions, research ethics and integrity regulations, open access practices (use of open data repositories, open-source software, etc.);
7. The method for the **assessment of the performance and impact** of the CSHs.

1.3 Approach

The governance frameworks, along with the operating models, were drafted through inputs from the co-creation workshops (Task 2.1) and additional inputs collected with individual conversations with each RPFO. The drafts were discussed and validated with the key stakeholders of the partner RPFOs through four workshops (one workshop run by each RPFO under the coordination and guidance of CC-CS), with a view to streamlining the frameworks to the stakeholders' expectations. The workshops were held in January 2022. The outcomes of this task (T2.2) are summarized in this 'Citizen Science Hubs Governance Frameworks and Operating Models--report, which serves as the foundation for the set-up of the CSHs in WP3.

1.4 Structure of the report

Chapter 2 illustrate the general approach of this task and the prework that has been done to define the governance frameworks and operating models for each CSH. In Chapter 3 the ‘baseline’ governance and operating elements, as defined in the project’s proposal, are outlined. Then, the vision and objectives of each RPFO’s CSH (Chapter 4) as well as their specific governance and operating elements (Chapter 5) are explained in detail. The report closes with a short conclusion and an outline of the next steps.

2. Approach and Prework

2.1 Co-Creation Workshops as starting point

The results of the co-creation workshops of Task 2.1, which took place in June and September 2021, were used as baseline to elaborate on the governance frameworks and operating models. In three sessions, under guidance of DesignLab/UT and based on its Responsible Futuring (RF)-approach, the four RPFO's co-created a blueprint of their individual CSHs together with the involved stakeholders. The three sessions focused on these phases of RF:

1. **Connect & Relate:** In the first workshop participants got to know each other and learned the perspective of each other with respect to their motives to be involved in CS;
2. **Understand & Frame:** In the second workshop participants agreed on the common frame for what CS is about and what not;
3. **Imagine & Ideate:** In the last workshop participants were working on designing their preferred (future) CSH.

Participants concluded the workshops by defining three (clusters of) activities for the ideal CSH that would provide the “pivotal aspects” of their governance frameworks and operating models. Then, they were asked how these activities would ideally be performed by answering questions such as “who is/are in the lead?”, “who is/are funding?”, “what area(s) of expertise is/are involved?”. Also, the participants were asked to arrange these activities in such a way to illustrate how a cluster of activities would relate to the core activities of the CSH and if a cluster of activities would be more university or society driven. With these assignments, participants laid the groundworks for the governance framework and operating model of their CSH. The main pivotal aspects are shown below (see Table 1).

Table 1: Pivotal aspects of the governance frameworks and operating models for each preferred CSH

RPFO	Key stakeholders*				Cluster of Activities	How to perform	Operational nodes
	A	G	PS	CiS			
AUTH	x	(x)	(x)	x	Lifelong Learning, Data Collection, Participatory Science and Partnerships	Local and regional partnerships; national and EU funding	Ethics, involving citizen and supporting CS communities
VG TU	x		(x)	x	Researcher, Awareness & Engagement, Agenda setting and Training & Education	Including “everyone”, structural changes needed in funding and training	Training, CS skills and Awareness & Engagement

UAB	x	x		x	Defining Challenges between UAB and QH, Engagement with Stakeholders and Engaging with new CS researchers	Training, network development, coordination, toll provision and sharing good practices of existing CS projects	CS project support, CS online tools & spaces, Communication & Dissemination and Training & Education
UT	x	x	x	x	Providing support to citizens on scientific methods and providing solutions for practical matters for citizens	Need of an infrastructure connected to existing social structures such as libraries	Communication & Dissemination

* A = Academia, G = Government, PS = Private Sector, CiS = Civil Society, (x) = limited presence

The detailed report on the workshops can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/record/5743299#.YjiQA5rMJN2>

2.2 Questionnaires

To understand better how each RPFO plans to establish its CSH, CC-CS elaborated a short questionnaire with questions providing additional and complementary information to the one collected in the workshops. The questionnaire included the following questions:

1. **Vision & Objectives:** What is your vision, mission, objectives? What are your values? Who are the stakeholders/parties involved in your CSH? What are the types of activities that people carry out in your CSH? What is the role that the CSH plays in the community?
2. **Facilities:** Is it a physical contact point, virtual or both? Why? What would be an acceptable initial setup?
3. **Organisational structure, roles, and responsibilities:** Where is the CSH located within your organisation? How does the governance structure look like? What positions/roles do you need? Which stakeholders should be included and at which level? What would be an acceptable initial setup?
4. **Procedures for use of CSH:** What are the procedures for the use of the CSH by professional researchers and by other stakeholders? What are the criteria to support projects? Which kind of ethical/legal support will you need? How do people interact in your CSH?
5. **Code of conduct:** Who are the parties involved in your CSH? What are their rights and obligations? What are the benefits/value that you are providing to your citizens, and how can you make sure you deliver them? How will you address ethical and legal considerations?
6. **RRI-related principles:** What are the CSH's effects on the environment and society? Express the general principles of the CSH concerning gender equality, research ethics and integrity, and open science approaches. How does the CSH provide practical reward for embracing RRI?

7. **Performance assessment & impact:** How do you assess the performance, the scientific impact and the social impact of your CSH?

Based on the integration of the different sources of information and complemented when needed with further individual discussions with the respective RRFO, CC-CS drafted four governance frameworks and operating models. The drafts were then taken back to RPFOS and their stakeholders and discussed one more time during four individual workshops (see 2.3) before finalization.

2.3 Workshops

The aim of these workshops was to clarify any potential doubts or uncertainties following the merge of information from the different sources, to integrate potential last-minute details, and to make sure all partners agreed with the proposed governance frameworks and operating models. This included comments of key stakeholders of each RPFOS, either participating in person or sending their view on the final drafts via consortium's representatives.

The workshops (one workshop per RPFOS) were organized under the coordination and guidance of CC-CS and run in January 2022. The format was similar for all of them and included:

- A short introduction of the project and tasks;
- An overview of each of the seven aspects of the governance structure and operating model, including a comparison with the solutions of the others RPFOS;
- Discussion on the specific solutions;
- Finalization of the governance structure and operating model that will be the baseline for setting up and operating the citizen science hubs (under WP3).

Participants in the different workshops reflected the past and ongoing collaboration of the RPFOS with other stakeholders, and the implementation of CS activities. Some of the stakeholders were also present during the session. In particular:

- **Workshop AUTH (January 20, 2022)**
The workshop was attended by 10 participants including the Vice Rector for Research and Lifelong Learning, 5 Researchers (PhD candidates and post-doc), 1 Professor, 1 representative from AUTH's Training and Lifelong Learning center, 1 representative from AUTH's Quality Assurance Unit and 1 representative from AUTH's Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation.
- **Workshop UAB (January 27, 2022)**
Prior to this workshop (joined by 2 staff members of UAB in charge of implementing the INCENTIVE project) the UAB team organised a participatory online session with 8 participants from the University (4 researchers, 3 Strategic Challenges-oriented Communities coordinators, and the ECIU University Local Ambassador) to validate this framework and complement it with their suggestions.
- **Workshop UT (January 17, 2022)**

The workshop at UT was held together with UT's Shaping Expert Group on Citizen Science (SEG-CS).¹ This SEG-CS gathers a wide diversity of UT staff both faculty and supporting staff that representing the various faculties of the university. Led by a Sponsoring Director and SEG Lead, the SEG is a temporary expert group that brings together two scientific experts from various domains, two organisational experts, a student representative and a marketing & communication specialist from the central Strategy Department. The SEG-CS aims to be connecting initiatives, sharing knowledge and skills within the organisation and supporting new initiatives and projects to arise. The SEG-CS is encouraging people from a wide variety of scientific disciplines to contribute to the group by sharing ideas and input. One domain is that of Health & Wellbeing.

- Workshop VGTU (January 28, 2022)

The workshop was attended by 4 participants including the Vice Rector for studies, Vice-dean for Research and 2 researchers. Led by 2 researchers implementing the INCENTIVE project, the online session was focused on validation of the framework and strategic goals of the hub (both short-term and long-term).

¹ More information on the SEG-CS can be found here: <https://www.utwente.nl/en/organisation/about/shaping2030/organisation/seg-citizen-science/#join-our-journey> (accessed 3 March 2022)

3. Baseline Governance and Operating Elements

UT, UAB, AUTH, and VGTU will be ultimately responsible for setting up and operating their CSH in alignment with the definition of the “*cooperative, active and responsible participation in science*” chosen by the partners as foundation of the CSHs (see Section 1.1). However, to ensure a consistent approach for their operation, partners of INCENTIVE developed and suggested a standard or “baseline”, set of elements for the governance, operating, and monitoring model for the hubs that define the objectives, activities, and the means to monitor results. RPFOS were inspired by these elements and then defined their own hub taking into account the specificities and circumstances of their own organization. This chapter illustrates the baseline elements.

3.1 Mission and Objectives

Along the lines of a cooperative, active, and responsible participation in science, the baseline mission and objectives of the CSH have been agreed upon among INCENTIVE consortium’s partners and defined in the initial project proposal as follow.

Mission: The mission of our CSHs will be to build capacity and engage all R&I stakeholders in science, grounding RRI in society.

Objectives: The objectives of the CSHs will be to:

- Drive a continuous process of institutional change opening up their RPFOS to become more “porous” to inputs from R&I stakeholders;
- Engage citizens, (professional) scientists and other R&I stakeholders to participate in citizen science aimed at addressing problems and societal challenges;
- Build and contribute the expertise required to co-design and run high quality, excellent citizen science projects in line with RRI;
- Support sustainable development efforts, by co-producing actionable knowledge.

3.2 Governance Framework

A governance framework refers to the governance structure of the organization and delineates the power and the governing or management roles. Frameworks define objectives, policies, values, culture, accountabilities, rules, procedures, and guidelines, and provide for the enforcement of these processes. In practice, a governance framework provides a mechanism for senior management, as well as those at the operational level, to have a clear understanding and oversight of each other's role, expectations, objectives, and performance.

As a baseline for the CSHs governance, INCENTIVE partners were inspired by the example of CC-CS’s Citizen Science Centre, and suggested in the initial project proposal the following governance structure:

Board of Directors (BoD): The BoD is made up of two to three faculty members (scientists, professors) of the founding RPFO(s). Members are elected by the Stakeholder Board and determine the chairperson of the BoD and their representative. They meet once per semester and are responsible for personnel, finance, and operational management.

Stakeholder Board (SB): The SB is the ultimate decision-making body of the CSH and is comprised of members from all R&I stakeholders (for more information on CSH’s membership see further below). The members of the SB meet at least once a year. The chairperson of the BoD convenes and chairs the SB.

Implementation team: The implementation team functions under the direction of the BoD and implements the activities of the Citizen Science Hubs, including a Secretariat, Facilitator, Community Manager and a Trainer: the Secretariat is the central point of administration; the Facilitator helps the implementation team, understand their common objectives, plan how to achieve them and work better together; the Community Manager is in charge of the management and development of the hub’s community of R&I stakeholders, and the Trainer is tasked with building capacity for and supporting stakeholders in designing and running RRI-underpinned citizen science projects.

Members: The membership of the Citizen Science Hubs will be open to citizen scientists, community groups and civil society organisations, student groups, researchers and academic faculty, as well as individuals from other R&I stakeholder groups including the industry, government bodies and public authorities.

Figure 1: Overview of the baseline Governance Structure, inspired by the CC-CS structure, and suggested by the INCENTIVE consortium to RPFOs as baseline element

3.3 Operating Model

An operating model is “both an abstract and visual representation (model) of how an organization operate to deliver value to its customers or beneficiaries as well as how an organization actually runs itself.” (Wikipedia). Given any organization, rather than describing what type of value is generated, an operating model determines how the value is generated and can be seen, in its simplest form, as a sequence of steps that describe the main work and activities of the organization (value delivery chain).

The elements of an operating model include structure, accountabilities, governance, essential behaviours as well as the way people, processes and technology get integrated. As it depends on dynamic elements, changes can occur quite regularly in the model. Also, an organization may have an operating model that describe the way the organization works today, and one to communicate the vision of how operations will work in the future (which is more the case in this document).

Key activities foreseen for each CSHs and suggested in the initial proposal include:

- Design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of projects engaging citizens and other R&I stakeholders to participate in science and to tackle societal challenges.
- Supporting citizen science projects with technical expertise and know-how to ensure their compliance with RRI principles as well as the co-production of high quality and relevant results.
- Design, implementation and monitoring of awareness raising campaigns on citizen science as well as encouraging public participation in science.
- Set-up of local stakeholder engagement events to inform and mobilise R&I stakeholders towards participating in citizen science as well as for catalysing connections and opportunities for new citizen science projects.
- Capacity-building of scientists and enhancing the literacy of citizens and R&I stakeholders in regional ecosystems to participate in science in line with RRI.
- Organisation of mutual learning activities to foster knowledge exchange (on good practices, lessons learned, etc.) and network opportunities with other Citizen Science Hubs and stakeholders.
- Keeping track and streamlining activities based on feedback from stakeholders towards a case for added value and vital role to contribute to science and grounding RRI in society.

4. RPFOS' Vision and Objectives

As a first step, it is necessary to elaborate the vision, mission and objectives for each CSH, aligned with the general vision of the respective RPFOS. While the vision describes what the CSH hopes to become in the future, the mission captures the key elements of the CSH's (past and) present and describes the CSH's identity, providing an answer to the question "Who are we?". The CSH's vision and mission combined offer a broad, overall sense of the CSH's direction. To work toward achieving these overall aspirations, the CSHs also need to define objectives.

To help the RPFOS better define these important aspects of their CSH strategy, they have been invited to further reflect on relevant components such as values, involved stakeholders/parties, planned activities, as well as what role the CSH plays for and in the community.

The outcomes are summarized in Figure 2 and 3, and detailed below.

Figure 2: Overview of the key points for the CSHs' vision, as provided by each RPFOS

Figure 3: Overview of the key points for the CSHs' objectives, as provided by each RPFOS

4.1.1 UT CS Hub

Vision: A permanent CS centre of expertise to facilitate a permanent CS community between science and society.

Mission: A visible, inclusive, and publicly accessible CSH that builds upon existing initiatives (e.g. TOPFIT CitizenLab, EnschedeLab, Science shop SMART) and will be competitive on an (inter)national level with CS knowledge and skills.

Objectives: Support a CS movement at UT; provide (improved) CS methods; start CS research projects; initiate CS modules; build a CS infrastructure (data, ethics, legal aspects and establish consortia) and maintain a CS community.

Values: Open access/open science values (i.e., openness, equality, integrity, respect, honesty) and the values of science education (learning, authority, reciprocity); ethically responsible; supporting regional wellbeing.

Stakeholders of the CSH: Academia (incl. UAS), government (e.g. regional, local), private sector and civil society.

Activities in the CSH: Build communities and projects; Provide (online) tools, infrastructure & spaces; Integrate solutions for data and ethics; Map CS initiatives and stakeholders; Develop an educational programme and skills training; Increase science literacy; Communication & dissemination.

Role of CSH to community: Mediating between science and society; facilitating citizens asking questions to and learning about science; connecting to existing social structures, projects, and initiatives.

4.1.2 UAB CS Hub

Vision: The CSH aims to tackle societal challenges in the territory with the participation of the quadruple helix by developing new models of teaching, doing research, and promoting innovation.

Mission: The CSH is building upon existing CS initiatives and resources, which when coordinated, can facilitate the development of CS at the University to promote the contribution to societal challenges.

Objectives: Promote the implementation of CS in any phase of the scientific process at the University by developing a CS Community at UAB; create synergies, share ideas and resources related to CS; create incentives for researchers to apply CS.

Values: all RRI-related values, especially inclusiveness and responsibility

Stakeholders of the CSH: QH, including the research, students and staff community at UAB, research centres related to UAB, B-30 association stakeholders, municipalities, Vallès Occidental and Vallès Oriental County Councils, Diputació de Barcelona, Metropolitan Area of Barcelona, Spin-offs of UAB, UAB Research Park, Clusters of enterprises, PIMEC (employers' association that represents the micro, small and medium-sized enterprises and the self-employed of Catalonia), SMEs associations, high school (secondary education), libraries, neighbours' associations, NGOs, Foundations, Fundació Autònoma SolidàriaB

Activities in the CSH: Provide resources to facilitate researchers' implementation of CS projects (legal and ethical advice, overview of CS projects, overview of co-creation spaces and tools, CS methodology, facilitator, apps builder for CS); provide an internal collaboration space among researchers; link to other CS Hubs in Europe; develop map of CS researchers (via the UAB research portal), develop a CS skills profile and deliver related skills training.

Role of CSH to community: Bring citizens closer to science by involving them in the scientific process; train critical citizens; promote the research carried out at the University.

4.1.3 *AUTh CS Hub*

Vision: create, maintain, and foster an open, inclusive, and sustainable ecosystem to support research and innovation based on the active participation and collaboration with civil society.

Mission: provide high quality services to connect science with society, including infrastructures and digital applications; expand and share knowledge (new courses); inspire innovation; promote research through public and community engagement; support the development of start-ups.

Objectives: offer opportunities and resources for learning, research and innovation; raise awareness on the CS benefits for science, society, economy and the environment; support participatory practises between academia and the civil society; facilitate the development of new competencies and skills; ensure improved transfer of knowledge and technology; eliminate bureaucracy in any administrative aspects.

Values: scientific excellence & innovation; diversity & inclusiveness; openness & transparency; responsiveness & adaptation; responsibility & accountability.

Stakeholders of the CSH: academia; students; researchers; citizens; civil society organizations; local authorities; entrepreneurs.

Activities in the CSH: co-creation; networking with supporters and collaborators; matchmaking; training; access to support infrastructure (e.g., IT services, research resources and material); communication and dissemination; engagement of diverse parts of the community (age, backgrounds, gender etc.).

Role of CSH to community: point of contact between stakeholders and facilitator of CS activities; provider of best practices; connector of NGOs or other fragmented programs that provide solution to citizens to contribute to science or research.

4.1.4 *VGTU CS Hub*

Vision: To create a platform supporting community and partners of Vilnius Tech in conducting Research & Innovation based on active engagement of civil society and principles of RRI.

Mission: To provide high quality resources, training and services to the community and partners of Vilnius Tech to promote active engagement of civil society into Research & Innovation process based on RRI principles.

Objectives: To raise awareness about benefits of Open Science, CS, and principles of RRI; to prepare training resources in local language; to promote the implementation of RRI, CS and Open Science principles into different stages of the research process; to create networking opportunities for community members willing to participate in co-creative research; to facilitate the development of new competencies and skills in Vilnius Tech.

Values: Life-long learning; creativity; co-creation; openness & transparency; sharing of know-how; community-driven.

Stakeholders of the CSH: All Quadruple-Helix quadrants – long term. In the shorter term, the stakeholders include The National Creative and Cultural Industries Association, KOG Marketing and Communication Science Institute, The Bored Panda start-up collective in Vilnius.

Activities in the CSH: Communication and dissemination with a focus on awareness raising on RRI, Citizen Science and Open Science principles; network building and maintenance (with special focus given on sharing the know-how and finding partners with relevant experience, tools); strengthening international cooperation with partners having experience with RRI, Citizen Science and Open Science; education and training of the community.

Role of CSH to community: provider of resources, training, and networking opportunities; intermediary between researchers and wider society.

5. RPFOS' Governance and Operating Elements

In the following, based on the baseline elements as defined in Chapter 3 and on the inputs gathered in the pre-work activities, the specific elements and procedures for each of the RPFOS are described as envisaged by them and deemed necessary to sustainably embody the CSH with the overall operation of each organization. The relations and interconnections of such elements (i.e., governance, facilities, procedures, code of conduct, RRI principles, and performance and impact assessment) are schematized in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Overview of relations and interconnections among RPFOS governance and operating elements

5.1 Facilities

It is important to decide – aligned with each CSH's strategy – if the hub will be a physical and/or virtual contact point. Both options have benefits, and each RPFOS should choose the best option based on factors such as the size of the team, availability of resources, and organization's culture and preferences.

A virtual hub refers to the option of providing the CS team, researchers, and citizens access to a joint platform and collaborative virtual working space. The positive sides include lower costs (no need for lease, furniture, supplies, equipment) and no need for commute, while negative aspects concern mainly the disconnection

among all involved, that can bring inefficiencies and potentially lack of trust. In current times (pandemic), a virtual option should always be envisaged at least for short term operations.

A physical hub may say a lot about the relevance of - and support to - CS within the hosting organization, and about the way the hub operates. Although more costly, it may facilitate opportunities and networking (for instance by working with an “open house” policy where researchers/citizens can just walk in and seek information and support).

Another relevant aspect to consider is the location of the hub, which can be inside the RPFO (easily accessible and visible for researchers), or in the city centre (easier for the public), or “mobile” (ie. pop-up presence at events or institutions). A combination of the three options is possible as well, depending mainly on available resources. Concerning resources, special attention should be given to the long-term financing of whichever option is chosen.

All RPFOs expressed the desire to create both a physical and virtual hub. Reasons for the physical presence included trust, facilitated co-creation, importance of in-person relations, better support the hub’s vision by facilitating knowledge sharing and engagement. The virtual presence, in the form of a website, is instead considered essential for resource availability and sharing, and to reach out to a wider audience.

The approaches are summarized in Figure 5 and detailed below.

Figure 5: Overview of the main features of the CSHs' facilities, as provided by each RPFO

5.1.1 UT facilities

UT is considering a permanent virtual hub complemented by a “pop-up” physical hub(s) more connected to society. UT will start by setting up a digital presence (website) to provide resources, ethical and legal solutions, and facilitate connection to existing initiatives. A more permanent physical hub could be located at DesignLab. UT is also working on a CS data infrastructure that should be accessible during the piloting phase of the project.

5.1.2 UAB facilities

UAB is considering a physical contact point located at the Rector's Office. The hub will connect with existing centralized (UAB OpenLabs, including the Metropolitan Laboratory of Ecology and Territory of Barcelona

(LET), COMTECH Centre, International Projects Office, Ethics Commission, Faculties, Libraries, Fundació Autònoma Solidària (FAS)) and decentralized (Living Labs, HUB B-30) spaces and services at UAB to provide resources and services to the CS researchers. Also, it will integrate EGRETA (UAB research portal, where the profiles of the researchers can be consulted) to promote the collaboration with researchers. UAB will start by setting up a website gathering all existing resources.

5.1.3 *AUTh facilities*

AUTh highlighted several barriers to the establishment of a physical hub, including lack of interest, doubts on the methodology, poor communication, mistrusts, mismatching between scientific agendas and local communities' needs.

AUTh will start by focusing on the implementation of a virtual presence to reach and engage with a wide audience of stakeholders, and that will allow for easier scale up of activities. It will also help eliminate most of the bureaucracy and administrative aspects that seem to be particularly heavy. Potential issues of ethics and privacy should also be a priority.

AUTh is in the city centre of Thessaloniki. Often the University organizes activities that invite citizens to visit the University and participate. AUTh assess the possibility of establishing an InfoPoint related to CSH outside of the University campus as a first step to bring University closer to citizens and raise awareness about CS, the hub and its activities.

5.1.4 *VG TU facilities*

Vilnius Tech is focused on the creation of a virtual hub complemented by physical activities (pop-up) when necessary (especially for training). For the physical activities, VG TU can take advantage of the existing facilities of the Faculty for Creative Industries, which can help with IT equipment such as hardware and software, and a physical place for people to meet and exchange problems and ideas. The virtual hub will start by setting up a dedicated institutional website with resources on CS, RRI and Open Science in local language and provision of available training opportunities.

The bureaucratic procedures necessary for the creation/assignment of a physical space at the University are very time consuming so VG TS is not currently considering the establishment of a physical hub.

5.2 Governance Models, Roles and Responsibilities

The proposed baseline for the governance structure and organizational models is illustrated in 3.2, inspired by the CC-CS hub existing in Zurich. Each CSH adjusted this baseline to imagine a structure that would fit their RPFO's needs and requirements. However, it is a difficult exercise as it will also depend on which unit within the RPFO the CSH will be administratively assigned – which is currently still unknown.

The desired structures are summarized in Figure 6 and detailed below.

Figure 6: Overview of the Governance Structure for each CSHs, as proposed by each RPFO

For the model of the governance of the RPFOs the following was suggested:

5.2.1 UT governance

Governance model:

- Steering Group: with academic and non-academic stakeholders to oversee the CSH's impact, finances, and general strategy;
- Operational Team: consisting of a coordinator, a community manager and operations and supporting students (reports to the Steering Group);
- Advisory Board: for strategic advice and to ensure we build on existing scientific and social knowledge (reports to the Steering Group);
- Theme Leads: (i.e., living environment/sustainability, health, digitalisation) to ensure access to the right bodies of knowledge and research, and advice the coordinator and community manager (reports to the Steering Group).

Positions/roles and their responsibilities: could be distributed to:

- Additional support staff: (e.g., communication and dissemination) might be added to the Operational Team to increase its operational capacities;
- Additional supporting student teams: can be added to the Operational Team and/or the Theme Leads for the organization of events and supporting research activities such as inventorying or exploring;
- Community manager: is responsible for building up and maintaining the CSH community. He/she need to be supported by internal and external networks and/or communities to ensure a strong and continuous involvement of QH partners.

Involvement of stakeholders: The start of the CSH fully depends on a permanent and high involvement of local and regional stakeholders as the hub needs to be embedded in the region to change the university into a more 'civic' university.

Initial set-up: UT will build upon existing initiatives such as TOPFIT CitizenLab, EnschedeLab, ECIU, SMART-ER. An initial set-up of UT's CSH will consist of a digital go-to place (website), core Operational Team (see

above), its strategy including communication and a (temporary) Steering Group. It will start focussing on one domain (Health), and will expand that to themes such as Biodiversity, Energy Transition.

5.2.2 UAB governance

Governance model:

- Stakeholder Board: representatives of the public administration, the private sector, the civil society and the academia will meet periodically to get an update on the activities and impact of the CSH;
- Board of Directors: Vice-Rector for International Relations, Vice-Rector for Research and Transfer, Vice-Rector for Innovation and Strategic Projects, Head of the Institutional Projects Office, Technical coordinator of ECIU University;
- Operational Team: Technical Staff and Structural Staff who work on facilitation of co-creation sessions and communication in UAB, and, if possible, an intern;
- Collaborators: Some leading CS researchers at UAB.

Positions/roles and their responsibilities:

- A Coordinator: to coordinate the implementation of the actions of the CSH;
- Technical Staff: to be the central point of contact, to implement the activities of the CSH and be in charge of all the administrative aspects of the CSH;
- Facilitators of co-creation sessions (with a Systems thinking mindset): to support researchers in the co-creation sessions with 4H stakeholders for the implementation of their CS projects;
- A Community Manager: to promote the participation of the 4H stakeholders in the hub's activities.

Initial set-up: will include a part-time involvement of facilitators, community manager, coordinator, community of CS. The Stakeholder Board and the Board of Directors will be formed soon.

5.2.3 AUTH governance

AUTH is thinking about a new independent unit (no specific department) that will operate under the supervision of the Senate of the University.

Governance model:

- CSH board: including the heads of participating labs and a hub director appointed by the governing body;
- Hub Manager;
- Topic Managers (e.g. researchers, PhD candidates, post-doc, students).

Involvement of stakeholders: citizens, representatives of CSOs, local authorities and professional associations could participate as external observers (committee).

Initial set-up: An initial small governing body (members are the heads of participating labs) and a dedicated team of facilitators (labs members & researchers) with experience in co-creation and networking.

5.2.4 VGTU governance

Governance model:

- **Institutional Board:** the board will include the heads of participating labs and a hub director appointed by the University Senate. The institutional board is in charge of setting up the strategic agenda for the Hub and ensuring its successful running by appointing the necessary resources and personnel;
- **Implementation team:** including a dedicated team of project managers and facilitators with experience in public engagement and co-creation. The team oversees preparing training resources, organizing educational seminar and networking activities;
- **External experts:** citizens, representatives of local authorities and associations, business and social partners could participate as external observers;
- **Members:** the membership in the Vilnius Tech Hub will be open to citizen scientists, community groups and civil society organisations, student groups, researchers and academic faculty as well as individuals from other R&I stakeholder groups including the industry, government bodies and public authorities.

Positions/roles and their responsibilities:

- **Hub Director:** coordinating the work of the Hub;
- **Member of Implementation Team:** could be sourced from support/administrative staff, researchers strongly supporting ideas of Open Science; students (especially PhD students).

Involvement of stakeholders: starting with The National Creative and Cultural Industries Association, KOG Marketing and Communication Science Institute, The Bored Panda start-up collective in Vilnius.

Initial set-up: An initial working group with the lead of Hub Director is already set-up at the Faculty of Creative industries (including project coordinator, Dean and Vice-Deans of the Faculty). The goal of the working group will be to establish the Hub at the institutional and start awareness raising activities (preparation of resources in local language and organization of training seminars).

5.3 Procedures of CSH Use

Procedures are a set of step-by-step instructions that need to be complied by each hub to describe the operation and use of the CSH by professional researchers of the RPFO, as well as by other stakeholders. They will benefit the hub by reducing misunderstandings, increasing efficiencies, creating a transparent work environment, and producing guidelines for how to resolve any potential issues. Given the early stage of the CSH implementation, procedures are work in progress for the RPFOs.

We highlight here the development plans and main concepts behind them.

5.3.1 *UT procedures*

Procedures for the use of the CSH by professional researchers: The CSH will develop procedures for the use of the CSH to make sure that students, early career and experienced researchers and support staff (i.e., Grant Office), support each other and exchange on methods, methodologies, and approaches. The CSH becomes a centre of expertise.

Procedures for the use of the CSH by other stakeholders: Non-academic stakeholders will be invited to use the CSH equally as their academic counterparts. Practical solutions to allow this will be further explored (based on existing initiatives).

Criteria to support projects: Projects by the CSH should contribute to its vision and mission. Especially at the beginning, the criteria to support projects is highly depending on the operational capacity that is available at the CSH.

Ethical/legal support: Based the current experiences and knowledge of the UT's Ethics committee and Legal department and existing initiatives that were mentioned above, UT will establish full ethical and legal clearance for the CSH activities e.g., disclaimers, user agreements, consent procedures and a code of conduct.

5.3.2 *UAB procedures*

Procedures for the use of the CSH by professional researchers: UAB CSH is developing procedures to describe how the hub will support researchers with writing proposals (incorporating the CSH) and by providing CS-related resources to support the facilitation of participatory sessions. They will include how to get advice on the submission of proposals, for example getting in touch with the International Projects Office, with researchers from their field or from others, contacting the COREs (Strategic Challenges-Oriented Communities at UAB), or checking the research portal (EGRETA) or the internal directory. Other procedures under development include how to participate in activities, such as meetings, workshops or conferences that the CSH might organise.

Procedures for the use of the CSH by other stakeholders: The resources of the CSH might be used by external actors from the territory (e.g., municipalities).

Criteria to support projects: Projects should comply with the general principles of CS to be able to receive general support. To be able to receive specific support (such as the facilitator), it will depend on the type of projects, the project funding, and the funding of the CSH.

Ethical/legal support: CSH will follow the UAB Code of Good Practice in Research (CBPR) approved in 2012; the procedures of the UAB Ethics Committee on Animal and Human Experimentation (CEEAH) and the ones of the UAB Data Protection Officer at UAB when implementing Citizen Science projects. Regarding legal considerations, the CSH will be assisted by the Legal Cabinet.

5.3.3 *AUTh procedures*

Procedures for the use of the CSH by professional researchers: The application will need to fulfil several criteria (linkage to existing projects; experience of the Project manager; existing infrastructure; sustainability plan; and existing financial support).

Procedures for the use of the CSH by other stakeholders: All citizens can apply and participate in the CSH's activities in a completely voluntary basis. There will be transparent procedures and terms for other stakeholders and citizens to enable informed consent for their participation. Overall, all parties will have: the right to use and benefit from the CSH's services based on the user agreement they enter with the CSH; the right to be adequately informed of the purpose and scope of the activities in which they are involved and to be treated lawfully and with respect; their lawful rights to their own data as dictated by the relevant legislation.

Criteria to support projects: The main criteria are the scientific and innovation value of the project; the feasibility of the project's implementation planning; the relevance of the project's objectives with the CSH's local ecosystem needs; the alignment with the CSH's objectives & values; the quality of the project; the experience of the Project manager; the existing infrastructure; the sustainability plan; the existing financial support; the active research team; the ethical, legal concerns and considerations.

Ethical/legal support: The CSH will guarantee to follow all EU and national regulations regarding data protection, ethics, privacy, and security. The CSH will develop a Data Management Policy in line with the EC & FAIR Data Guidelines and will assign a Data Protection Officer (DPO) responsible to apply transparent informed consent procedures as well as procedures for keeping all data secure.

5.3.4 *VGTU procedures*

Procedures for the use of the CSH by professional researchers: The team will develop procedures for the use of the Hub to make sure that experienced CS-researchers support each other with projects, grants, proposals, and in general exchange on methods, methodologies, and approaches. Networking activities will play a central role in this process.

Procedures for the use of the CSH by other stakeholders: The team is setting transparent procedures and terms for Vilnius Tech community members to join activities of the Hub. The focus of these procedures will be ensuring an informed consent for their participation.

Criteria to support projects: Criteria will be developed based on quality criteria developed by ECSA and consultations with Lithuanian citizen science association (to ensure that any existing local peculiarities will be addressed).

Ethical/legal support: Collaboration with the Vilnius Tech legal teams and Ethics committee will ensure that the Hub will follow all EU and national regulations regarding data management and privacy. Documentation such as disclaimers, user consent forms and code of conduct will be prepared.

5.4 Code of Conduct

A code of conduct explains what constitutes appropriate and inappropriate behaviour within an organization. The code is based on the hub's principles and visions and forms the basis for further concrete guidelines and regulations, laying down the moral and ethical expectations that all parties involved are held to as they interact with the CSH.

The most common elements to include in a code of conduct are:

- Ethical principles (e.g., workplace behaviour and respect for all people);
- Values (e.g., honest, unbiased and unprejudiced work environment);
- Accountability (e.g., taking responsibility for your own actions, ensuring appropriate use of information, exercising diligence and duty of care obligations and avoiding conflicts of interest);
- Standard of conduct (e.g., complying with the job description, commitment to the organisation and proper computer, internet and email usage);
- Standard of practice (e.g., current policies, procedures and operational manuals);
- Disciplinary actions (e.g., complaints handling and consequences for any violation of the code).

5.4.1 *UT code of conduct*

UT is taking as inspiration for its code the rights and obligations of Open Access and FAIR DATA. The UT will establish ethical and legal clearance, consent procedures, and a code of conduct (see above).

5.4.2 *UAB code of conduct*

For UAB is crucial that all parties involved in the CSH (UAB community, high schools, libraries, municipalities, etc.) should find benefit, in particular the public by getting science education and the researchers by getting the resources they need. UAB will establish data and ethics procedures based on the advice of the Ethics Committee, the Data Protection Officer and the legal department, considering already existing procedures that researchers must follow, such as the UAB Code of Good Practice in Research (CBPR).

5.4.3 *AUTh code of conduct*

CSH at AUTh will design and conduct all its operations promoting responsible action, reflecting upon the wider impacts of the stakeholders' work, and supporting the public good with respect for the human rights and freedoms as described in the European Convention on Human Rights. The CSH will oversee all activities to monitor the respect for individuals and human dignity, the rights and interests of all research stakeholders, and the fair distribution of burden and benefits, while at the same time staying in line with the CSH's objectives and protecting its values.

5.4.4 VGTU code of conduct

Vilnius Tech will base their code of conduct on principle of co-created value. This means that not only the institution, but the participants will benefit from participation in Hub activities. Legal and ethical documentation in support of Hub activities will be prepared with the help of legal team and Ethics Committee. Since public engagement elements are not widely addressed in institutional or national documents shaping the Research & Innovation, good practice analysis will be conducted in order to integrate relevant elements (e.g. FAIR data principles).

5.5 RRI-related Principles

The CSHs need to adhere to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles. This approach aims to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation by anticipating and assessing their potential implications and societal expectations.

According to the European Commission *“Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society”* (<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>. Accessed 10/03/22) In practice RRI is an umbrella term that incorporates six key dimensions: ethics, societal engagement, gender equality, open access/science, science education; and sustainability & social justice/inclusion.

INCENTIVE’s RPOs have focused on some dimensions relevant to CS research and innovation, namely: effects on environment and society, gender equality, researcher ethics and integrity, open science approaches and practical reward for embracing RRI.

5.5.1 UT RRI-related principles

Effects on environment and society: UT is in the process of selecting which societal challenges the hub will focus on. The initial focus will be on one domain to keep it manageable.

Gender equality: UT strives to create a safe learning and working environment including a House of Integrity, its diversity of Twente programme, a “Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Team”, and a recent Gender Equality Plan. In its operations, being at the borders of the university environment, the CSH will follow its own principles, guidelines and advice.

Researcher ethics and integrity: see under “gender equality”.

Open science approaches: Open Access and FAIR data, as pillars of Open Science.

Practical reward for embracing RRI: to be decided.

5.5.2 UAB RRI-related principles

Effects on environment and society: CSH will tackle both environmental and societal challenges, as UAB is already very active in the implementation of environment-related CS projects.

Gender equality: contribute to the IV Action Plan (2019-2023) of the Observatory for Gender Equality at UAB; promote the gender perspective in research.

Researcher ethics and integrity: follow the UAB Code of Good Practice in Research (CBPR) approved in 2012.

Open science approaches: contribute to the Action Plan for Open Access at UAB of the 2013 created UAB Open Access Commission. We aim to create an Open Science portal at UAB.

Practical reward for embracing RRI: will provide resources and support for the implementation of CS projects which embrace RRI. If possible, offer a Prize for the best research in CS.

5.5.3 ATh RRI-related principles

Effects on environment and society: the hub will advocate responsible and sustainable practices for all its supported activities and projects undertaken by its members with environmental impacts.

Multiple social impacts:

- Enhances society's trust in science by ensuring that scientific and research agendas are well aligned with societal challenges and actual needs;
- Empowers citizens with a deeper and broader understanding of how science works and cultivates an open-minded and critical approach on all topics of the public dialogue;
- Spreads the spirit of cooperation and teamwork among various social groups and communities;
- Strengthen social cohesion by fostering inclusiveness, pluralism and respect for the views and contributions of others;
- Open science principles and the democratisation of access to knowledge and innovation addresses social exclusion and positively impacts social mobility;
- The engagement of citizen groups and communities in the Hub's activities towards achieving common R&I goals activates citizens and stimulates their interest in the commons and their surroundings;
- Develop scientific literacy, new skills and competencies in fields that are relevant to citizens and affect their lives and environment.

Gender equality: The CSH will prioritize women participation by:

- Formulating a non-discrimination policy to assess and resolve any potential gender-discrimination related issues;
- Following a gender balance-balanced approach in all activities and citizens inclusion;
- Seeking a gender equality in recruiting for trainers and its own staff;
- Encouraging female participation in entrepreneurship and innovation;

- Pursuing links and co-operation with relevant associations and organizations.

Researcher ethics and integrity: The CSH will uphold the highest professional standards for research ethics and integrity in the conduct of its activities by:

- Adhering to the ethical principles of autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, and justice for all research and activities involving human participants;
- Providing an ethical policy that sets out the framework within which the ethical review process of each activity will operate;
- Monitoring ethics and integrity of all supported CS projects and activities;

Open science approaches: Open Science practices, including accuracy, accountability, and reproducibility of research are fundamental for the CSH. The CSH is committed to making its research outputs findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable by implementing an open science centric strategy within all its activities:

- Active involvement of citizens and all actors in the R&I process from the beginning;
- Tools and material, data and code continuous availability, reproducibility, and transparency;
- Early and open sharing of research outputs;
- Measures to ensure uptake of research outputs (dissemination, open publications, use of open research repositories, etc)

Practical reward for embracing RRI: The main practical rewards will be the certificates; the micro credentials; the clear results exploitation strategy and user agreement to ensure fair IPR management and recognition of citizens contributions.

5.5.4 VGTU RRI-related principles

Effects on environment and society: The hub will advocate responsible and sustainable practices in all activities. Since Vilnius Tech is a multi-disciplinary university covering wide-research areas with a special focus on sustainable buildings, environmental and energy technologies, sustainable transport, artificial intelligence and inclusive & creative society, the potential impacts are broad.

Gender equality will be promoted through following a gender balance-based approach in civil society inclusion, employment of Implementation Team, constitution of Institutional board.

Researcher ethics and integrity: Vilnius Tech Hub will uphold the highest professional standards for research ethics and integrity in the conduct of its activities through development of Code of Conduct and setting up of monitoring process to make sure that activities adhere to the regulation. The activities of the Hub will also adhere with [Vilnius Tech's Code of Ethics](#).

Open science approaches: Vilnius Tech Hub is committed to making its research process transparent and outputs – findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). The activities will adhere with [Vilnius Tech's Open Access policy](#).

Practical reward for embracing RRI: The practical rewards are mostly intangible. The training activities will provide community members with a new perspective and actionable insights on new and innovative ways on how to conduct research. One possible way to make these rewards more tangible is through issuing certificates after completion of trainings. Networking also could enrich the participants by providing access to like-minded individuals and organizations.

6. Performance and Impact Assessment

In the frame of WP4 «Monitoring, evaluation and assessment», the INCENTIVE project provides CSHs with a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) framework, developed within T4.1, to assess and monitor their operation and performances, including stakeholder engagement actions, CS projects and their outcomes. The M&E framework includes a set of assessment instruments (e.g. indicators, tools, procedures, and more) to capture data before, during, and after the pilots activities of the hubs, allowing a timely monitoring of the efficacy of the different hub's approaches to drive institutional changes.

Integrating the M&E framework within the governance structure and/or operating models adds much value to the CSHs, as collected data can be used to:

- Identify the strong and weak parts of their operating model, infer the success and prohibiting factors, and improve their activities and overall approach;
- Understand the CS community (internal and external stakeholder), its motivation, characteristics and other specificities. Then, based on this information, CSHs can improve their future planning and allocation of resources;
- Collect evidence on the hub's societal, scientific, economic and environmental impact. If presented to stakeholders and policymakers, this evidence could trigger interest in CS and potentially yield greater funding.

This section provides a summary of the M&E framework, emphasising its operational part. CSHs can adapt the framework to their specificities and implement it both in the context of the project and after the project is completed.

For the initial phase, namely the activities aimed at establishing and integrating the new hub within the RPFO, the following main methods for monitoring and evaluation are suggested:

- **Method 1: CS Project questionnaires**
The main activity of a CS hub is to facilitate CS projects. Thus, monitoring those projects' performance, outcomes, and impacts is crucial. CS hubs are encouraged to seek to receive feedback both from the researchers and the citizens participating. From an operational perspective, the feedback could be collected by the person leading the project (CS project leader) and processed by the CS Hub secretary.
- **Method 2: CS Hub report**
Except for the above projects, CS hubs usually implement other various activities that serve their purposes. For instance, they implement R&I co-creation activities (e.g., R&I agenda setting), capacity building activities (to strengthen science literacy), mutual learning and networking events. The hubs are encouraged to seek feedback from these activities' participants and aggregate their responses into a CS Hub report.
- **Method 3: RPFO report**
In many RPFOs, citizen science is used as a lever of change for the broader integration of RRI principles into their activities and operation. Also, the CS hub can be truly valuable only if properly

integrated into the operation of the RPFO. Monitoring the above can be crucial. Data could be aggregated in a dedicated RPFO report.

- Method 4: Stakeholder interviews

Finally, it is of utmost importance for a CS hub to be in touch with the local community. For instance, it's crucial to know whether stakeholders find good and useful the hub's activities and if, overall, they appreciate the hub's social, economic, democratic and environmental impact. Thus, the CS hubs are advised to interview several of their stakeholders. A handy and effective method is the Most Significant Change approach. It is an interview-based approach that asks stakeholders to tell their personal stories of how they experienced the most significant change that took place within the RPFO.

Implementing the above methods allows CS hubs to collect valuable data that is required to assess progress towards key objectives, such as:

- O1. Grounding RRI in society
 - O1a. Promoting good practice in citizen science
 - O1b. Cultivating a more scientifically interested and literate society
 - O1c. Enhancing fruitful stakeholder interactions
- O2. Transforming how RPFOs create impact and interact with their surroundings
- O3. Advancing sustainable development at the local, regional, and global level
 - O3a. Making progress towards the SDGs
 - O3b. Creating societal, economic, democratic scientific impact

Finally, CS hubs are encouraged to process the data collected to get useful insights. They can assess and evaluate their performance and impacts as depicted by specific indicators by comparing the values of the indicators with their targets, with the results of other RPFOs, with the expectations of their stakeholders and with relevant worldwide trends. The process of target setting should precede any monitoring. It must consider the profile and the specificities of the RPFO, the baseline situation and the resources available for CS projects and other relevant activities. The stakeholders' expectations can be used for evaluation purposes and captured in two ways: (i) by interviewing them or (ii) by inviting them to a meeting where the results of the hub are presented, and then, stakeholders are invited to provide feedback.

CS hubs are welcome to propose improvements to the above approach and implement changes to adapt the framework to fit their specificities. At the same time, they are invited to plan the framework deployment considering the allocation of roles and the resources available.

7. Conclusions and Next Steps

With the help of the entire consortium, the four RPFOs of INCENTIVE have successfully defined the governance structure and operating model of their CSH in all their conceptual and operational parts, as well as the RRI-related aspects. Inspired by the set of baseline elements provided by the consortium, the teams at each RPFO worked internally and with local stakeholders to accommodate constraints and requirements specific to the different administrative and cultural frameworks of their institutions. The multiple occasions of exchange and interaction provided by the supporting partners, including both formal meetings and informal gatherings and calls, and featuring various models of engagement (workshops, online boards, questionnaires) turned out to be very useful for mutual learning, reciprocal inspiration, sharing and clarification of common questions and doubts. All RPFO have now a clear idea on what required to sustainably embody the CSH within the overall operation of their own institutions, including facilities, governance, processes, standards, regulations, resources. Thanks to the Monitoring & Evaluation Framework provided by WP 4, they also know which data to collect in order to assess and monitor their pilot activities and assess the success of their institutional integration.

This work will contribute to several ongoing and upcoming tasks. Based on this knowledge, Task 2.3 (“Manual and tools for incentivising and engaging quadruple helix stakeholders in the Citizen Science”) will develop the methodologies and tools to incentivise, engage and enable quadruple helix stakeholders to participate in the activities of the CSHs. The new hubs will start with activities as suggested in report of Deliverable 2.4 (“Defining the activities to be pursued by the Citizen Science Hubs”), focusing mainly on raising awareness about the existence of the hub, supporting CS projects, and establishing a CS network with institutional and local stakeholders.

Each RPFO’s team will be trained in the context of Task 3.2 (“Training on the set-up and operation of the Citizen Science Hubs and mutual learning between frontrunner and beginner”), focused on fostering mutual learning and knowledge exchange between partners that already have some experiences in designing and implementing processes for institutional change (SDA Bocconi, UT, UAB) and partners that are considered beginners (AUPh, VGTU). This will include training on the way to follow the methodological guidelines as developed by Task 2.5 (“Methodological guide and digital toolkit for setting-up and running new Citizen Science Hubs”).

As part of the ongoing Task 3.3 (“Set-up and operation of the Citizen Science Hubs to ground RRI in society”) each partner RPFO - after having identified the location of the facility that will act as a single point of contact for CS (see Chapter 5 of this document) - will assign responsibilities and roles to the staff that will undertake the operation of the CSH, including the implementation teams and the other envisaged governance bodies.

Finally, in the context of monitoring and assessment activities, the hubs will monitor their performance in coordination with Task 4.2 (“Monitoring the performance and impact of the Citizen Science Hubs”), with a particular attention to constantly assessing and adapting their activities to the needs of their stakeholders.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

COORDINATOR

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (DesignLab)

PARTNERS

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (DesignLab)
www.utwente.nl/en/designlab

UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA
www.uab.es

ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS
www.auth.gr

VILNIAUS GEDIMINO TECHNIKOS UNIVERSITETAS
vilniustech.lt

UNIVERSITAT ZURICH
www.uzh.ch

UNIVERSITA COMMERCIALE LUIGI BOCCONI
www.unibocconi.eu

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS
qplan-intl.gr

WHITE RESEARCH SRL
white-research.eu

VEREIN DER EUROPAEISCHEN BURGERWISSENSCHAFTEN – ECSA
ecsa.citizen-science.net

CONTACT US

info@incentive-project.eu

- [incentive-project](#)
- [incentiveH2020](#)
- [incentive-project](#)
- [incentive_eu](#)

